

Windfarm Re-Scattered Clutter Mitigation in HF OTHR with 2D Receive Antenna Arrays

Yuri I. Abramovich
WR Systems
Fairfax, VA 22030 USA

Geoffrey San Antonio
US Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, DC 20375 USA

Abstract—Massive windfarms located in front of high frequency over-the-horizon radar (HF OTHR) receive (Rx) antenna arrays modulate strong backscattered ground clutter returns and re-scatter these modulated returns towards the Rx array. In this paper it is shown that these windfarm modulated returns propagated via a ground wave path can be rejected by the optimum processing in 2D Rx antenna arrays with elevation selectivity. We investigate the efficiency of windfarm interference mitigation in Rx arrays with different 2D geometries and specify an optimum geometry for a particular windfarm location with respect to a given RX antenna array.

Index Terms—HF OTHR, windfarm interference

I. INTRODUCTION

Widespread expansion of electrical power generating windfarms has already created compatibility problems with various radar systems located too close to these windfarms [1]. Particular problems arise when large windfarms with hundreds of massive wind turbines are located in the vicinity of HF OTHR antenna arrays. It is well known that modern HF OTHR operates in the presence of very strong ground returns. Indeed, subclutter visibility (SCV) at the output of Doppler processing should reach up to ≈ 90 dB for the successful detection of small moving targets. When this strong skywave propagated backscattered clutter signal arrives on the windfarm, it becomes modulated by individual turbines so that the bandwidth of the re-scattered clutter Doppler spectrum is much broader than the bandwidth of the original clutter. In the case of windfarms located beyond the visual line-of-sight horizon from the Rx array, this re-scattered signal propagates via a ground wave to the Rx array. Even for poor soil conditions such as dry earth, the attenuation over this path may be insufficient to completely hide these modulated clutter returns below the external noise level. In some cases, the windfarms are located in shallow sea waters [2], which can dramatically reduce the surface/ground wave propagation losses. Therefore, in all those cases where the ground wave propagation losses are insufficient to fully attenuate the re-scattered strong clutter returns, one has to consider special measures to counter the windfarm interference impact. Obviously, since windfarm interference is just a re-scattering of normal radar clutter, an increase in radar power cannot alone help mitigate the interference and thus other strategies must be considered.

The random-like nature of the integrated turbine modulation effect leaves no room for optimization in the range-Doppler

frequency domain by a proper choice of radar waveform and/or range-Doppler processing. The only possibility is in the exploitation of the difference between the spatial wavefront properties of normal skywave radar returns and ground-wave windfarm interference. Specifically, we can exploit the difference between the zero elevation angle-of-arrival windfarm interference and the non-zero elevation angle skywave returns. The spatial difference is explored in this paper.

II. OPTIMAL RX ANTENNA BEAMFORMING FOR WINDFARM INTERFERENCE MITIGATION

In our analysis, skywave propagated far-field signals are described by the traditional plane-wave manifold fully specified by azimuth (Az, θ) and elevation angle (El, ϕ) (from the horizon). For a point source, located at a distance R from the receive antenna array, the ground-wave propagated wavefront is described by a spherical manifold specified by (R, θ) . Therefore, even a 1D linear antenna array with no elevation selectivity has the potential to resolve plane vs. spherical wave signals arriving from the same azimuth. Indeed, consider an M -element uniform linear array (ULA) with inter-element spacing d , and assume a signal arriving from a distance R , $Az=\theta$. Then two opposing effects define the output signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR) at the output of the optimal beamformer, steered into the far-field (plane-wave) direction-of-arrival θ . On the one hand, the smaller the distance R is, the smaller the ground-wave attenuation of the interference signal and therefore the greater the input interference-to-noise ratio (INWR) at the antenna array element. On the other hand, the distinction between the spherical and plane-wave manifold grows with the smaller distance, which in turn means that mitigation of the spherical wavefront should cause smaller degradation in SNR for the plane-wave signal. Therefore, unless the wind turbine re-scatter can be completely removed through ground-loss attenuation that ensures the interference level is below the external noise at the output of a plane-wave beamformer steered in the direction θ , there is always an optimal distance within the range $\{R_{min}, R_{max}\}$ that balances path loss, turbine radar cross-section (RCS), external noise power, and spherical wave defocusing. For example, let us consider an artificial example with the single source at the point (R, θ) with changing R , but constant interference-to-white noise ratio (INWR) at the input of an M -element ULA with a certain d/λ . Then the output SINR, normalized to SNR

Fig. 1. Defocusing factor - Array length $D = 2093\text{m}$

in the absence of the spherical-wave interference is equal to

$$\begin{aligned} \eta^2(\theta, R) &= \frac{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) [\mathbf{I} + q_{int}^2 \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R) \mathbf{s}_{sp}^H(\theta, R)]^{-1} \mathbf{s}(\theta)}{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{s}(\theta)} \\ &= 1 - \frac{q_{int}^2 |\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R)|^2}{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{s}(\theta) (1 + q_{int}^2 \mathbf{s}_{sp}^H(\theta, R) \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R))} \\ &\leq 1 - \rho^2(\theta, R) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\rho^2(\theta, R) = \frac{|\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R)|^2}{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{s}(\theta) \mathbf{s}_{sp}^H(\theta, R) \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R)} \quad (2)$$

and $\mathbf{s}(\theta) \in C^{M \times 1}$, $\mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R) \in C^{M \times 1}$, are the M -variate manifold M -element ULA vectors for far-field (plane-wave) and near-field (at the distance R from the array center) source in $Az=\theta$. In fact, $\rho^2(\theta, R)$ practically does not depend on θ , and in figure (1) we present the dependence of the “defocusing factor” $\rho^2(R)$ as a function of R for an $M=300$ element ULA with $d=7\text{m}$ and $f=24, 12, 10, 5$ MHz at distances R ranging from 1km to 100km . From figure (1) it follows that SNR losses associated with (complete) mitigation of the near-field source are always smaller for a larger antenna aperture (measured in wavelengths) and the data suggest how the INR has to change with R so that the maximal available distance is the optimal one. The traditional boundary between the near-field and far-field, defined as D^2/λ , is 350km , 175km , 146km , 73km for the four frequencies specified.

Unfortunately, a more detailed study of this optimal distance does not make a lot of practical sense since very rarely if ever is a single wind turbine erected on its own. In practice a large number of wind turbines are erected as part of a single windfarm and they occupy a certain azimuthal sector, which quickly reduces the efficiency of windfarm interference mitigation in 1D ULA’s to practically insignificant levels. The explanation of this phenomenon follows from the fact that an ensemble of spherical manifold vectors $\mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta, R)$ with $(\theta, R) \in A(\theta, R)$ quite accurately spans a certain subspace of the plane-wave manifold vectors $\mathbf{s}(\theta)$ for some $\theta \in A(\theta)$ where $A(\theta)$ is the azimuthal extent of the area $A(\theta, R)$ occupied by a entire windfarm. This phenomenon is illustrated below. Therefore, the only reliable distinction that remains for a large number of wind turbines is the difference between the zero elevation angle of the ground wave returns vs. the non-zero elevation angle of the “proper” skywave returns. Yet

the minimal elevation angles for skywave returns are quite low; for ionospheric E-layer ($h_e = 100\text{km}$) and maximal ranges, the elevation angles can be as low as $\phi = 3^\circ$ [3]. For most scenarios with F-layer returns the elevation angles lie within the interval $5^\circ - 20^\circ$. Obviously a 2D antenna array with the optimal beamformer that places a null at zero-elevation angle, but has reasonably low losses at say $\phi = 5^\circ$, should have a minimum depth. In this regard, in what follows we consider practical antenna and windfarm geometries, and investigate SINR performance in optimal beamforming for different antenna arrays.

First consider a $M=372$ element ULA with $d=7\text{m}$ and the (embedded) antenna element beampattern, described as short (Hertzian) monopole over a lossy ground [4], i.e.

$$g(\phi, \theta) = c \sin^2(\phi) \cos^{0.7}(\phi). \quad (3)$$

Here ϕ is the elevation angle calculated off zenith. In (3) $g(\phi, \theta)$ is the element far-field beampattern and therefore has zero gain not only at the zenith direction $\phi = 0^\circ$, but also for the grazing direction (at the horizon) $\phi = 90^\circ$. For near-field ground wave propagated signals (3) is not correct, so we characterize the input windfarm interference power by its interference-to-internal white noise ratio (JINR). External HF noise is uniformly distributed in azimuth, but in elevation is confined by the critical elevation angle (for a given frequency and ionospheric conditions). In [5] it was demonstrated that the external noise distribution at operations close to the maximal usable frequency (MUF) is accurately described by the power distribution

$$w(\phi, \mu) = c \sin^\mu(\phi). \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the M -variate covariance matrix of the mixture of windfarm interference, external noise, and internal noise is calculated as

$$\mathbf{R}_{i+n} = \mathbf{R}_{wf} + \mathbf{R}_{ext} + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}. \quad (5)$$

The analytical expression for \mathbf{R}_{ext} for arbitrary 2D antenna arrays, $g(\phi, \theta)$ specified in (3) and $w(\phi, \mu)$ specified in (4) is derived in [5].

$$\mathbf{R}_{wf} = \sigma_{wf}^2 \frac{1}{Q} \sum_{j=1}^Q \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta_j, R_j) \mathbf{s}_{sp}^H(\theta_j, R_j) \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta_j, R_j)$ is the normalized ($\mathbf{s}_{sp}^H(\theta_j, R_j) \mathbf{s}_{sp}(\theta_j, R_j) = 1$) manifold of a near-field source at (θ_j, R_j) , and Q is the total number of wind turbines. A comparison of different 2D Rx geometries with respect to a 1D ULA is performed with quantitative metrics provided by signal-to-noise (external and internal) ratio (SNR) and signal-to-interference plus noise ratio (SINR). Specifically we asses

- 1) Optimal Beamformer SNR (in windfarm interference absence)

$$\text{SNR}_{opt} = \mathbf{s}^H(\phi, \theta) \mathbf{R}_n^{-1} \mathbf{s}(\phi, \theta) \quad (7)$$

- 2) Optimal Beamformer SINR

$$\text{SINR}_{opt} = \mathbf{s}^H(\phi, \theta) \mathbf{R}_{i+n}^{-1} \mathbf{s}(\phi, \theta) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Windfarm location relative to 1D ULA

3) Optimal Beamformer SINR loss

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{loss}} = \text{SINR}_{\text{opt}} / \text{SNR}_{\text{opt}} \quad (9)$$

4) Optimal Beamformer 2D SINR relative to ULA SINR

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{opt}}^{2D/ULA} = \text{SINR}_{\text{opt}}^{2D} / \text{SINR}_{\text{opt}}^{ULA} \quad (10)$$

5) Optimal Beamformer 2D SINR relative to ULA SNR

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{opt}}^{2D/ULASNR} = \text{SINR}_{\text{opt}}^{2D} / \text{SNR}_{\text{opt}}^{ULA} \quad (11)$$

In what follows we simulate a quite realistic windfarm consisting of 151 wind turbines. Its location with respect to the 1D ULA Rx antenna array is illustrated figure (2). As follows from figure (2) the distance between the array center and the closest turbine is about 20km. The 1D ULA considered in this analysis consists of 372 short monopoles with $d=7\text{m}$ inter-element spacing. One alternative 2D Rx antenna array is a uniform rectangular array (URA) with the same inter-element spacing. In this analysis we consider external-to-internal white noise ratios (EINR) that are realistic for daytime operations, or about 10dB EINR at a single antenna element. In addition we consider windfarm interference-to-internal noise ratios (JINR) of 20dB, which is 10dB above the external noise power at a single antenna element. Such unrealistically large JINR more typical of “proper” skywave clutter-to-noise ratios is selected specifically to investigate the potential interference mitigation efficiency.

Let us start from the analysis of the ULA performance in the presence of noise only and noise plus windfarm interference. The beamsteer elevation angle is kept the same for 1D ULA and 2D URA arrays ($\phi = 85^\circ$) though for ULA this means just a shift in the resulting coning angle. First, in figure (3), we introduce the 1D ULA gain in SNR for the noise only case for a signal at $f=25\text{MHz}$, sufficiently close to the $d/\lambda = 0.5$ condition. One can see that the specific external noise distribution makes the SNR gain in the 1D ULA azimuth dependent, ranging from 17.7dB to 21.6dB (in

Fig. 3. 1D ULA SNR in noise only

boresight direction). In figure (4) we introduce the SINR, and finally in figure (5) the optimal beamformer SINR loss for the 1D ULA ($\text{SINR}_{\text{opt}} / \text{SNR}_{\text{opt}}$). From figures (4-5) it follows that in directions to the windfarm ($\theta = 30^\circ$), practically no interference mitigation is possible and practically the full antenna gain ($\approx 23\text{dB}$) amplifies the windfarm interference power at the output of the optimal 1D ULA beamformer. Naturally for this windfarm interference to be fully unharmed (SINR losses equal to zero dB everywhere) the input JINR should be equal to -20dB instead of +20dB considered in this example (40dB difference). Let us now compare the SNR and SINR metrics for the prior 1D ULA and a 2D URA consisting of 4 rows of the same 372-element 1D ULA. SNR and SINR results for this 2D antenna array are illustrated by figures (6,7,8,9). One can see that a 4-times increase in the number of antenna elements improved both SNR and SINR in the 2D array compared with the 1D more than 4dB everywhere outside of the “windfarm sector” around $\theta = 30^\circ$. Within this sector, we observe $\approx 15\text{dB}$ better performance than in the 1D ULA, despite the fact that with respect to other directions for this 2D URA, we still lose $\approx 30\text{dB}$. Therefore, if keeping SNR performance at the 1D ULA level in every beamsteer direction is the design goal, it could be achieved in this 4×372 URA with $\text{JINR}=-5\text{dB}$, instead of $\text{JINR}=20\text{dB}$ for the 1D ULA. In a similar manner, figure (10) illustrates SINR performance for a 8×372 URA. One can see that compared with the 1D ULA in the azimuth region of the “windfarm sector” it is now possible to gain 20dB of SINR, which now makes $\text{JINR}=0\text{dB}$ a tolerable level.

In the above analysis we considered the use of 2D URA’s, but for operations over a reasonably low beamsteering elevation angle the inter-row distance may be increased without the danger of creating a grating lobe within the elevation beamsteer sector of interest. In figure (11,12) we introduce the familiar results on SNR and SINR performance assessment for a 2D URA with the inter-row spacing set at $d=14\text{m}$. It

Fig. 4. 1D ULA SINR gain

Fig. 7. 2D URA SINR loss

Fig. 5. 1D ULA SINR loss

Fig. 8. 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

Fig. 6. 2D URA SINR gain

Fig. 9. 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

Fig. 10. 8x372 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

Fig. 12. Sparse depth 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

Fig. 11. Sparse depth 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

Fig. 13. 2D URA SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain at 20° Elevation

is evident that this 4×372 URA with depth equal to the original 8×372 URA provides almost the same benefit with half the number of elements. Note that the results are derived for the very low elevation angle $\phi = 85^\circ$. For the 1D ULA the elevation angle is irrelevant, but for the 2D array the bigger separation between ground-wave propagated windfarm interference returns and skywave beamsteer directions makes a significant difference. For the 4×372 URA ($d=7m$) and $EI=20^\circ$ ($\phi = 70^\circ$) optimum beamformer steered into $(70^\circ, \theta)$, $\theta \in 30^\circ \pm 4^\circ$ provides 39dB of SINR improvement with respect to the 1D ULA and total SINR loss is reduced to 3dB from 40dB, figure (13). This analysis demonstrated that even a relatively “thin” 2D antenna array can significantly improve OTHR performance in the presence of weak enough windfarm interference.

It is important to note that 2D URA’s have a number of other features that are important in different OTHR scenarios. For this reason, the 2D URA geometry considered in this

analysis cannot be treated as the one specifically optimized for a particular windfarm interference mitigation scenario. Naturally, there is the question about the best geometry of N -elements augmenting the existing 1D ULA for the specific purpose of windfarm interference mitigation. Let us assume that in addition to the existing $M = 372$ element ULA we may deploy an additional 400 elements to achieve the best interference mitigation for the particular windfarm configuration presented in figure (2). Note in this regard that this particular windfarm occupies a relatively limited azimuthal sector which suggests that most of our resolution capability in elevation should be concentrated within this limited sector. If all the wind turbines were aligned along a single azimuthal direction, then a single orthogonal auxiliary arm should be a proper solution. Since the windfarm scenario in this analysis has a non-zero but finite azimuthal width, we found that two orthogonal arms separated by 800m with 200 elements per arm and inter-element spacing $d=13m$, see figure (16) provides

Fig. 14. 2x Orthogonal Arm 2D Array SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SNR Gain

Fig. 15. 2x Orthogonal Arm 2D Array SINR gain relative to 1D ULA SINR Gain

very good mitigation efficiency across the OTHR frequency range (5-30MHz). Specifically, for the beamsteer elevation angle $\phi = 85^\circ$, the worst SNR losses compared with the 1D ULA in the absence of interference, do not exceed 2dB in the optimum 2D beamformer, figures (14,15).

III. CONCLUSION

Two-dimensional (2D) receive antenna arrays can provide sufficient mitigation of ground-wave propagated broadband modulated clutter signals re-scattered by wind turbines located in the vicinity of receive OTHR antenna arrays. The “depth” required of a 2D uniform array depends on path-loss attenuation and interference-to-internal noise ratio, with 4 rows or 8 rows the uniform rectangular array with optimum beamforming provided sufficient interference mitigation in most cases. For relatively strong windfarm return mitigation, a specific 2D antenna geometry is required. For the the windfarm

Fig. 16. 2x Orthogonal Arm 2D Array

scenario considered in this paper, 2 orthogonal 200-element 2.7km long arms can mitigate even a very strong windfarm interference with less than 2dB degradation in SNR, when compared to the main 1D ULA array in the absence of the windfarm interference.

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